

Basic Six Pupils' Views About Science and Their Stereotypical Images of Scientists

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Abstract

This study explored Basic Six pupils' perspectives on science and scientists in Ghana using a convergent parallel mixed-methods design grounded in the pragmatist paradigm. A total of 40 pupils participated in the study and completed the Views About Science Questionnaire, Views About Scientists Questionnaire, Misconceptions About Science Questionnaire, and the Draw-A-Scientist Test (DAST). Quantitative and qualitative data were collected concurrently and integrated during analysis to provide a comprehensive understanding of pupils' perceptions. The findings revealed that many pupils held negative perceptions of science, stereotypical images of scientists, and mixed views of the nature of science. The DAST results further demonstrated persistent stereotypes, with most drawings portraying scientists as male, serious, working alone, and confined to laboratory settings. These portrayals reflect limited and sometimes inaccurate conceptions of scientific work. The results highlight the need to address misconceptions and stereotypical images of scientists in basic education to enhance pupils' engagement with science. It is recommended that schools adopt inquiry-based and contextually relevant science curricula, provide professional development for teachers on inclusive and stereotype-sensitive pedagogy, invest in modern laboratory and ICT resources, and develop partnerships with practicing scientists as role models. Such interventions may help cultivate more positive and realistic views of science and potentially increase pupils' interest in pursuing science-related careers.

Keywords: *scientists, science education, misconceptions, pupils' perceptions, draw-a-scientist test, stereotypical images, scientists.*

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Introduction

Science plays a vital role in contemporary society by driving technological advancements, improving health outcomes, and influencing everyday life (Osborne & Dillon, 2008). Its significance in shaping our world is profound, with discoveries and innovations transforming how we live, work, and interact. Science education is therefore essential in equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to navigate the complexities of the modern world.

Despite its importance, many children hold limited perspectives on science, often shaped by misconceptions and stereotypes (Archer et al., 2013). Concerns about the impact of stereotypical perceptions of scientists on children's attitudes toward science and their willingness to pursue STEM-related careers have prompted increasing research interest in children's conceptions of scientists (Leavy et al., 2023). Such perceptions can significantly influence students' interests, attitudes, and career aspirations. For instance, children who view science as boring, difficult, or relevant only to certain groups

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may be less likely to pursue science careers or engage with scientific issues in everyday life. Understanding how Basic Six students perceive science and scientists is critical to enhancing science education and promoting positive attitudes toward the subject.

Research suggests that children's perceptions of science are strongly influenced by their surroundings, including teachers, textbooks, media, and personal experiences (Chambers, 1983). These factors can either spark curiosity and passion for science or create barriers that discourage engagement. One particular challenge is the persistence of stereotypical views of scientists, which often portray them in limited ways, such as men in lab coats working in laboratories (Chambers, 1983). Such portrayals can reinforce narrow perceptions of scientific work and limit children's aspirations in science. In addition, science is frequently perceived as disconnected from daily life, preventing pupils from seeing its relevance to their experiences.

Lei et al. (2019) found that children were generally more interested in performing science activities than in becoming scientists. While they enjoyed engaging with science, they were less likely to envision themselves in scientific roles. Moreover, children believed that their competence in science would decline as they grew older. These findings suggest potential challenges in maintaining science interest and confidence across developmental stages. Previous research indicates that such declines may be mitigated by educational practices that provide exposure to diverse and relatable role models in science (Dennehy & Dasgupta, 2017) and support the integration of scientific practices into children's personal and social identities.

Statement of the Problem

Despite sustained efforts to improve science education, many children continue to hold misconceptions about science and scientists (Finson, 2002). These misunderstandings can influence students' perceptions of science, their engagement with scientific learning, and their career aspirations (Archer et al., 2010). For example, some children perceive science as inherently difficult and suited only for exceptionally intelligent individuals, which can create feelings of intimidation and alienation (Steinke et al., 2007). Others hold stereotypical views of scientists as older men wearing lab coats and handling dangerous substances. Such representations reinforce narrow, inaccurate, and sometimes negative images of the scientific profession (Steinke et al., 2007).

These stereotypes can discourage children from engaging fully with science and reduce their interest in pursuing science-related careers (Archer et al., 2010). Addressing these challenges requires intentional educational efforts that reshape children's perceptions of science, encouraging them to see it as a creative, collaborative, and accessible human endeavour rather than as an exclusive or intimidating discipline (Hodson, 2014).

Although there is a growing body of international research on children's perceptions of science and scientists, relatively little is known about how children in Ghana view science. Understanding these perceptions is essential for educators and curriculum developers who aim to design instructional strategies that make science meaningful, relevant, and accessible to young learners (Hodson, 2014). This study, therefore, seeks to examine the views of Basic Six pupils regarding science and scientists in Ghana, providing insights that can inform more inclusive and effective science education practices.

Literature Review

Students' View of Science

Students' perceptions of science play an important role in shaping their attitudes and motivation toward learning science. Research has consistently shown that students' views of science influence their academic achievement, career aspirations, and overall understanding of scientific concepts (Osborne et al., 2003). For this reason, understanding how students perceive science is essential for educators and policymakers who seek to design effective science education programs that encourage positive attitudes and sustained engagement with science.

Students' views of science are complex and multifaceted. They often include ideas about the nature of science, the processes of scientific inquiry, and the role of science in society. One prominent theme in students' views is empiricism, which emphasizes the importance of observation and experimentation in the development of scientific knowledge. Lederman (2007) notes that students commonly view science as a discipline that relies heavily on experimentation and data collection. This perception is reflected in students' emphasis on evidence-based reasoning and the use of empirical methods to test scientific ideas (Driver et al., 1996).

However, research also suggests that many students hold simplified or incomplete views about the nature of science. Empirical studies indicate that learners often perceive science as a body of fixed and unchanging knowledge rather than as an evolving enterprise that is open to revision and refinement (Lederman et al., 2013). When students adopt this absolutist view, they may interpret scientific knowledge as a collection of facts, rules, and formulas that must simply be memorized (Osborne et al., 2003). Such perceptions can limit students' understanding of how scientific knowledge is generated and how it develops over time.

Another important aspect of students' views of science relates to relevance. Relevance refers to the extent to which students perceive science as meaningful and applicable to their everyday lives. According to Aikenhead (2006), many students struggle to recognize connections between school science and their daily experiences. When students fail to see these connections, they may view science as abstract and disconnected from real life, which can contribute to negative attitudes toward science learning (Lyons, 2006).

Understanding students' views of science is therefore essential for developing effective science education practices. By recognizing the key ideas that shape students' perceptions of science, educators can design teaching approaches that promote deeper understanding and more positive attitudes toward the subject. Several strategies have been recommended to support this goal. For example, encouraging students to explore scientific ideas through hands-on activities and open-ended inquiry can help them understand how scientific knowledge is developed (Abrahams & Millar, 2008). Presenting science in meaningful contexts that highlight its applications in everyday life can also improve students' engagement and appreciation of science (Aikenhead, 2006). In addition, explicitly teaching students about the nature of science, including the role of evidence, the tentative nature of scientific knowledge, and the social context of scientific inquiry, can help students develop more accurate conceptions of science (Lederman, 2007).

Several factors contribute to the formation of students' views about science. Teaching methods, cultural influences, and media representations all play important roles in shaping students' perceptions and attitudes. Teaching approaches that rely heavily on teacher-centered instruction may lead to disengagement and reduced motivation among students (Abrahams & Millar, 2008). In contrast, inquiry-based learning and hands-on activities have been shown to promote greater interest and more positive attitudes toward science (Bybee, 2006).

Cultural and social contexts also influence how students perceive science. Students' cultural backgrounds and social environments may shape their understanding of who participates in science and what science represents. Some students may perceive science as elitist or inaccessible, particularly when they do not see people from their own backgrounds represented in scientific fields (Carlone & Johnson, 2007). Recognizing these influences allows educators to design more inclusive and culturally responsive science education programs.

Other factors that influence students' views of science include prior learning experiences, teacher-student relationships, and the nature of the science curriculum. Positive learning experiences, supportive teachers, and engaging curricula can contribute to more favorable perceptions of science. Educational strategies that promote positive views of science include encouraging inquiry and hands-on exploration, acknowledging the cultural and social contexts of scientific knowledge, and helping students critically evaluate media portrayals of science (Aikenhead, 2006; Abrahams & Millar, 2008; Nisbet & Scheufele,

2009). Through these approaches, educators can support students in developing a deeper and more accurate understanding of science and its role in society.

Children's Stereotypical Images of Scientists

Students' early experiences with science play a crucial role not only in the development of STEM literacy but also in shaping their perceptions of science and the work of scientists. The way science is presented to children, both inside and outside the classroom, strongly influences their understanding of who scientists are, what they do, and who can participate in scientific activities (Thomson et al., 2019). Early encounters with science, therefore, contribute to the formation of children's mental images of scientists and their understanding of scientific work.

Research consistently shows that children often develop stereotypical images of scientists from an early age. Children's drawings have been widely used as a methodological tool to explore these perceptions, particularly through the Draw-A-Scientist Test (DAST). Many studies report that scientists are frequently depicted as white males working indoors in laboratory environments and surrounded by chemistry-related equipment such as test tubes, flasks, and other glassware (Bernard & Dudek, 2017; Thomson et al., 2019). Thomson et al. (2019) further observed that children commonly portray scientists wearing laboratory coats and eyeglasses, often with exaggerated features such as wild or disheveled hair and unusual facial expressions. These depictions reinforce conventional stereotypes of scientists as eccentric or socially detached individuals. Although many drawings portray scientists neutrally or positively, the dominance of laboratory symbols and chemistry-related contexts reflects a limited view of scientific work.

Similar patterns have been reported across different age groups and cultural contexts. Bernard and Dudek (2017) found that children consistently depicted scientists working in indoor laboratory settings, often accompanied by laboratory glassware, notebooks, and blackboards. Likewise, Leavy et al. (2023) identified recurring stereotypical elements in children's drawings, including eyeglasses, laboratory environments, and symbols of scientific experimentation. Some drawings also included hazardous activities such as explosions or fire, suggesting that children may associate science with danger or dramatic experimentation. These findings suggest that children's images of scientists are influenced by traditional representations of science in school materials, media portrayals, and broader societal narratives about scientific work.

Despite the persistence of stereotypes, some studies indicate that children also attribute positive personal characteristics to scientists. For instance, Ruiz-Mallén et al. (2018) reported that students frequently described scientists as intelligent, hardworking, curious, and motivated. However, appearance-based stereotypes such as lab coats, eyeglasses, and male gender remained common in their representations. Similarly, Samaras et al. (2012) found that although children often depicted scientists using stereotypical imagery, many students described scientists positively as knowledgeable, gentle, and dedicated individuals. Nevertheless, a smaller proportion of children associated scientists with negative characteristics, such as being dangerous or "mad," which reflects lingering misconceptions about scientific practice.

These findings show that children's perceptions of scientists often combine positive attributes with persistent stereotypes related to gender, work environment, and the nature of scientific activities. The consistency of these representations across studies highlights the importance of addressing stereotypes early in science education and broadening students' understanding of the diverse roles and contexts in which scientific work occurs.

Students' views of scientists are also closely connected to their attitudes toward science and their interest in science-related careers. Research shows that students' perceptions of scientists can influence their motivation to learn science, their engagement with scientific topics, and their willingness to pursue careers in science and technology fields (Osborne et al., 2003). Early studies such as Chambers (1983) and later work by Stake and Mares (2001) demonstrate that students frequently associate scientists with characteristics such as eccentricity, social isolation, and distinctive clothing such as laboratory coats. When students internalize these stereotypes, they may struggle to see themselves as potential scientists.

Media portrayals of scientists can further reinforce these stereotypes. Scientists are often represented in films, television programs, and other media as brilliant geniuses or “mad scientists,” which may shape students’ perceptions of the scientific profession (Nisbet & Scheufele, 2009). When students adopt these narrow images of scientists, they may perceive science careers as inaccessible or incompatible with their own identities (Carlone & Johnson, 2007; Stake & Mares, 2001).

Teachers and role models also play an important role in shaping students’ perceptions of scientists. Exposure to diverse scientific role models can help students develop more realistic and inclusive views of science and scientific careers (Stake & Mares, 2001; Aikenhead, 2006). Teachers can influence students’ perceptions by presenting science in ways that highlight its relevance to everyday life and by emphasizing the collaborative, creative, and socially meaningful nature of scientific inquiry (Aikenhead, 2006; Osborne et al., 2003).

Students’ perceptions of scientists, therefore, have important implications for science education. When scientists are viewed as elitist, isolated, or inaccessible, students may feel excluded from science-related fields (Carlone & Johnson, 2007). In contrast, when students perceive scientists as relatable individuals engaged in meaningful work, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward science and consider pursuing science-related careers (Hativa, 2013; Stake & Mares, 2001).

To encourage more positive and inclusive views of scientists, several educational strategies have been proposed. These include providing students with opportunities to interact with practicing scientists, highlighting the diversity of people and careers within science, and presenting science in ways that connect with everyday experiences (Aikenhead, 2006; Stake & Mares, 2001). Through these approaches, educators can help students develop a more accurate and balanced understanding of science and scientists, which may ultimately support stronger engagement with science learning and future participation in science-related careers.

Materials and Methods

Design

This study was grounded in the pragmatic research paradigm, which supports methodological pluralism and allows researchers to select research methods that best address complex educational phenomena (Dube et al., 2024). Within this paradigm, both quantitative and qualitative approaches can be used to provide a comprehensive and context-sensitive understanding of the issues under investigation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

Accordingly, the study adopted a convergent parallel mixed-methods approach, which integrates quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques to generate deeper insights into pupils’ views of science and scientists (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In this design, quantitative and qualitative data are collected during the same phase of the research process, analyzed separately, and then integrated to provide a more complete interpretation of the findings.

Instruments

Four instruments were used to collect data in this study: the Views About Science Questionnaire (VASQ), the Views About Scientists Questionnaire (VASTQ), the Misconceptions About Science Questionnaire (MISQ), and the Draw-a-Scientist Test (DAST). The Views About Science Questionnaire (VASQ) was designed to assess pupils’ perceptions of science. It consisted of 10 Likert-type items with response options ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The items were developed by the researcher and reviewed by experts in science education to ensure face validity.

The Views About Scientists Questionnaire (VASTQ) was used to measure pupils’ views and possible stereotypes about scientists. This instrument also consisted of 10 Likert-type items using a five-point scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Similar to the VASQ, the items were developed by the researcher and subjected to expert review to establish validity.

The Misconceptions About Science Questionnaire (MISQ) was designed to identify common misconceptions pupils hold about science. The instrument consisted of five Likert-type items that used the same response scale as the previous questionnaires. The items were developed based on relevant literature and classroom observations and were reviewed by experts to ensure content validity.

The Draw-a-Scientist Test (DAST) was used to explore pupils' mental images and stereotypes of scientists. The instrument was adapted from the protocol developed by Ruiz-Mallén and Escalas (2012). Pupils were asked to draw a scientist working in a laboratory. The drawings were subsequently analyzed using established coding categories to identify recurring themes and stereotypical representations of scientists.

Validity and Reliability

Content and face validity of the instruments were established through expert review and iterative refinement (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). To establish content validity, the initial versions of the questionnaires, namely the Views About Science Questionnaire (VASQ), Views About Scientists Questionnaire (VASTQ), and Misconceptions About Science Questionnaire (MISQ), were reviewed by two experts in science education. The experts evaluated the relevance, clarity, and alignment of each item with the constructs being measured. Their feedback was used to revise ambiguous items, improve wording, and remove redundant items to ensure that the instruments adequately represented the intended constructs.

The Draw-a-Scientist Test (DAST) is a widely used qualitative instrument designed to elicit children's perceptions and stereotypes about scientists through drawings. In this study, the DAST was adapted from the protocol developed by Ruiz-Mallén and Escalas (2012). The content validity of the DAST was supported through the adoption of established coding frameworks from the literature (e.g., Chambers, 1983; Finson, 2002; Ruiz-Mallén & Escalas, 2012), which have been widely applied in studies examining children's depictions of scientists. These coding schemes include commonly identified indicators of stereotypical images of scientists, such as the presence of lab coats, eyeglasses, male gender, books, scientific equipment, and laboratory environments.

The internal consistency of the questionnaire instruments was assessed using Cronbach's alpha (α) reliability coefficient. Cronbach's alpha is a widely accepted statistical measure used to determine the extent to which items within a scale are interrelated and measure the same underlying construct (Taber, 2018). The Views About Science Questionnaire (VASQ) produced a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.82, indicating good internal consistency. The Views About Scientists Questionnaire (VASTQ) yielded a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.79, which reflects acceptable internal consistency. The Misconceptions About Science Questionnaire (MISQ) produced a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.74, which is considered acceptable for instruments containing a relatively small number of items (Field, 2018).

Trustworthiness of the Qualitative DAST Analysis

To enhance the trustworthiness of the qualitative analysis of the Draw-a-Scientist Test (DAST), inter-rater reliability was established through independent coding and comparison of results. Two coders independently analyzed the pupils' drawings using the predetermined coding rubric derived from established frameworks in the literature (Chambers, 1983; Finson, 2002; Ruiz-Mallén & Escalas, 2012). The coding scheme included indicators such as the presence of lab coats, eyeglasses, gender representation, laboratory tools, technological equipment, and other stereotypical attributes associated with scientists.

Before the full analysis, the coders jointly reviewed the coding categories and practiced coding a small subset of drawings to ensure a shared understanding of the coding criteria. Each coder then independently coded all drawings according to the established rubric. After the independent coding process, the results were compared to determine the level of agreement between the coders.

Inter-rater reliability was assessed using Cohen's kappa coefficient, which measures the degree of agreement between coders while accounting for the possibility of agreement occurring by chance. The

analysis yielded a Cohen's kappa value of 0.82, indicating a high level of agreement between the coders and suggesting that the coding process was reliable. Any discrepancies identified during the comparison were discussed and resolved through consensus, ensuring that the final coding accurately reflected the characteristics depicted in the drawings.

Sampling

The target population for this study comprised all Basic Six pupils enrolled at St. John Bosco's Basic School, located in Navrongo in the Kassena Nankana Municipal of the Upper East Region of Ghana. A sample of 40 pupils was selected from the school to participate in the study. The pupil sample was drawn using a simple random sampling technique. This method ensures that each pupil in the population has an equal probability of being selected, thereby minimizing selection bias and enhancing the representativeness of the sample (Ary et al., 2010).

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 27. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize pupils' views and perceptions regarding science and scientists (Field, 2013). Specifically, descriptive measures such as means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages were calculated to provide an overview of the response patterns. The results were presented using frequency tables and charts to facilitate clear interpretation of the findings (Ary et al., 2010).

The qualitative data from the Draw-a-Scientist Test (DAST) were analyzed using a modified version of the scoring rubric adapted from Ruiz-Mallén and Escalas (2012). The coding scheme consisted of several variables grouped into four main categories: Personal Traits, Elements of Scientific Knowledge, Human and Social Values, and Risk Acceptance. Most of the variables were coded dichotomously, where the presence of a particular feature was coded as 1 and its absence as 0.

This coding procedure allowed for a systematic examination of both stereotypical and non-stereotypical representations in pupils' drawings. The coded data were subsequently summarized using frequencies and percentages to identify common patterns in the drawings. Table 1 presents the variables and coding scheme used for the DAST analysis. In addition, Figures 1–3 provide sample drawings produced by pupils along with the corresponding coding.

Table 1. Variables and coding scheme of the DAST

SN	Variable	Description	Coding
1	Scman	Scientist depicted as male	1 = Yes, 0 = No
2	Scwoman	Scientist depicted as female	1 = Yes, 0 = No
3	Whitecoat	Scientist wearing a white laboratory coat	1 = Yes, 0 = No
4	Glasses	Scientist wearing eyeglasses or safety goggles	1 = Yes, 0 = No
5	Labtool	Presence of laboratory instruments such as test tubes, beakers, flasks, microscopes, or burners	1 = Yes, 0 = No
6	Techtool	Presence of technological tools such as computers, robots, electronic devices, or other digital equipment	1 = Yes, 0 = No
7	Location	Research setting depicted (e.g., laboratory bench, field site, observatory, or another identifiable research environment)	1 = Yes, 0 = No
8	Dishevelled	Scientist shown with disheveled, messy, or "crazy" hair	1 = Yes, 0 = No
9	Unfriendly	Scientist portrayed as serious, unfriendly, or stern (e.g., angry or non-smiling facial expression)	1 = Yes, 0 = No
10	Biochem	Depiction of biochemistry or chemistry research activities (e.g., test tubes, chemicals, reactions)	1 = Yes, 0 = No
11	Astrophys	Depiction of astronomy or astrophysics research (e.g., telescopes, planets, stars, space-related objects)	1 = Yes, 0 = No
12	Math	Depiction of mathematics research (e.g., equations, numbers, graphs without laboratory context)	1 = Yes, 0 = No

13	Environ	Depiction of environmental science research (e.g., plants, ecosystems, nature-based fieldwork)	1 = Yes, 0 = No
14	Technol	Depiction of technology or robotics research	1 = Yes, 0 = No
15	Artshum	Depiction of arts or humanities research	1 = Yes, 0 = No
16	Medicine	Depiction of medical or health-related research	1 = Yes, 0 = No
17	Multidis	Multidisciplinary scientific activities depicted (involving more than one field of research)	1 = Yes, 0 = No
18	Formula	Presence of written formulas, equations, symbols, or numerical representations	1 = Yes, 0 = No
19	Expt	Scientist shown conducting an experiment or manipulating scientific materials	1 = Yes, 0 = No
20	Think	Scientist shown thinking, reflecting, or observing rather than actively experimenting	1 = Yes, 0 = No
21	Teach	Scientist shown teaching, explaining, or presenting knowledge to others	1 = Yes, 0 = No
22	Crazy	Scientist portrayed as violent, malevolent, unstable, or unpleasant	1 = Yes, 0 = No
23	Danger	Presence of hazardous elements such as explosions, spills, fire, or dangerous chemicals	1 = Yes, 0 = No
24	Unsafety	Absence of safety equipment such as gloves, goggles, lab coat, or protective masks during experimental activities	1 = Yes, 0 = No
25	Solitary	Scientist depicted working alone without collaboration or interaction with others	1 = Yes, 0 = No

Source: Adapted from (Ruiz-Mallén & Escalas, 2012)

Figure 1. Sample DAST Drawing 1 (by pupil s/n 8, male student)

1. Scman (male scientist): no; 2. Scwoman (female scientist): yes (appears female); 3. Whitecoat: yes (clearly wearing a buttoned lab coat); 4. Glasses: no; 5. Labtool: yes (test tubes/beakers on the bench); 6. Techtool: no; 7. Location: yes (lab bench visible, suggesting a science lab); 8. Dishevelled: yes (messy hair with wavy lines); 9. Unfriendly: no (smiling); 10. Biochem: yes (test tubes suggest chemistry); 11. Astrophys: no; 12. Math: no; 13. Environ: no; 14. Technol: no; 15. Artshum: no; 16. Medicine: no; 17. Multidis: no; 18. Formula: no; 19. Expt: yes (test tubes, liquids, chemistry); 20. Think: no; 21. Teach: no; 22. Crazy: no (smiling, gentle appearance despite messy hair); 23. Danger: no; 24. Unsafety: no; 25. Solitary: yes

Figure 2. Sample DAST Drawing 2 (by pupil s/n 35, male)

1. Scman (male scientist): Yes (appears male); 2. Scwoman: No; 3. Whitecoat: Yes (lab coat with buttons); 4. Glasses: No; 5. Labtool: Yes (test tubes, funnel, beakers, lab equipment on the bench); 6. Tectool: No; 7. Location: Yes (laboratory table with science tools); 8. Dishevelled: No (neatly styled hair); 9. Unfriendly: No (smiling); 10. Biochem: Yes (presence of test tubes, liquids, chemicals); 11. Astrophys: No; 12. Math: No; 13. Environ: No; 14. Technol: No; 15. Artshum: No; 16. Medicine: no; 17. Multidis: No; 18. Formula: No; 19. Expt: Yes (laboratory experiment with funnel and beakers); 20. Think: No; 21. Teach: No; 22. Crazy: No; 23. Danger: No; 24. Unsafety: No; 25. Solitary: yes

Figure 3. Sample DAST Drawing 3 (by pupil s/n 4, male)

1. Scman (male scientist): Yes (appears male); 2. Scwoman: No; 3. Whitecoat: Yes (wearing a lab coat); 4. Glasses: Yes (clearly drawn with round glasses); 5. Labtool: Yes (holding a flask with liquid); 6. Tectool: No (the item on the right-hand side seems like a book or block rather than technology); 7. Location: Yes (laboratory table with science tools); 8. Dishevelled: No (neatly styled hair); 9. Unfriendly: No (smiling);

10. Biochem: Yes (using a flask suggests chemistry); 11. Astrophys: No; 12. Math: No; 13. Environ: No; 14. Technol: No; 15. Artshum: No; 16. Medicine: no; 17. Multidis: No; 18. Formula: No; 19. Expt: Yes (experimenting with Flask); 20. Think: No (no explicit thinking symbols); 21. Teach: No; 22. Crazy: No (although hair is exaggerated, expression is calm); 23. Danger: No (no flames, explosions, or danger signs); 24. Unsafety: No; 25. Solitary: yes

Results

Demographic characteristics

Figure 4 presents the sex and age distribution of the pupils. Out of 40 students, 21 (52.5%) were female, and 19 (47.5%) were male. Most of the participants, 26 out of 40 (65%), were aged between 10 and 12 years. The remaining 14 participants (35%) were above 12 years of age. This suggests that the sample was predominantly made up of younger children within the 10–12 age group.

Figure 4. Sex and Age of Pupils

Children's Views about Science

Table 2 summarizes children's views about science based on their responses to ten statements. The overall mean view about science was 2.44 (SD = 0.53), which suggests a generally negative perception of science among the children. Looking at individual statements, "Science is a subject that is only taught in school" had the highest mean score (M = 3.30, SD = 1.57). This suggests that many children wrongly view science narrowly as something confined to the school setting.

"Science helps us understand the world around us" (M = 1.60, SD = 1.08) and "Science is useful for solving real-life problems" (M = 2.25, SD = 1.26), showing that many children fail to appreciate these important roles of science. Similarly, children expressed weak agreement with the idea that science requires creativity (M = 2.18) or is essential for technological advancement (M = 2.30).

Table 2. Means and Standard Deviations of Children's Views about Science Scores (N = 40)

sn	Statement	M	SD
1	Science is about conducting experiments in the laboratory.	2.43	1.36
2	Science is a subject that only involves memorizing formulas and facts.	2.73	1.26
3	Science is a field that is separate from other subjects like math and language	2.33	1.59
4	Science is about discovering new things, not about applying them.	2.75	1.26
5	Science is a subject that is taught only in school.	3.30	1.57

6	Science helps us understand the world around us.	1.60	1.08
7	Science is useful for solving real-life problems.	2.25	1.26
8	Science is a subject that requires creativity and imagination.	2.18	1.22
9	Anyone can be a scientist, regardless of their background.	2.50	1.55
10	Science is essential for technological advancements.	2.30	1.51
	<i>Overall</i>	<i>2.44</i>	<i>0.53</i>

Pupils' Views about Scientists

Table 3 presents children's views about scientists, with a mean score of 3.00 or higher indicating a positive view, while scores below 3.00 indicate a negative view.

Table 3. Means and Standard Deviations of Children's Views about Scientists (N = 40)

<i>sn</i>	<i>Statement</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1	Scientists are always wearing lab coats and working with test tubes.	2.10	1.37
2	Scientists are geniuses who have a natural ability to understand complex concepts.	1.85	0.92
3	Scientists work in laboratories all the time and never go outside.	3.70	1.18
4	Scientists are always old and experienced.	2.85	1.35
5	Scientists are creative and intelligent people.	1.95	1.15
6	Scientists are mostly men.	2.45	1.43
7	Scientists are socially awkward.	2.38	0.95
8	Scientists work alone in laboratories.	2.98	1.27
9	Scientists are older adults with wild hair.	3.53	1.30
10	Scientists care only about facts, not people.	3.70	1.26
	<i>Overall Score</i>	<i>2.75</i>	<i>0.43</i>

The overall mean score for children's views of scientists was 2.75 (SD = 0.43), indicating generally negative perceptions of scientists. Three statements recorded relatively high mean scores: "Scientists work in laboratories all the time and never go outside" (M = 3.70, SD = 1.18), "Scientists are older adults with wild hair" (M = 3.53, SD = 1.30), and "Scientists care only about facts and not people" (M = 3.70, SD = 1.26). These responses suggest that many children strongly associate scientists with common stereotypes, portraying them as isolated individuals who spend all their time in laboratories and are primarily concerned with facts rather than people.

In contrast, several statements reflecting positive characteristics of scientists recorded relatively low mean scores. These included "Scientists are geniuses who have a natural ability to understand complex concepts" (M = 1.85, SD = 0.92), "Scientists are creative and intelligent people" (M = 1.95, SD = 1.15), "Scientists are socially awkward" (M = 2.38, SD = 0.95), and "Scientists work alone in laboratories" (M = 2.98, SD = 1.27). The lower ratings for these statements suggest that children do not strongly recognise attributes such as creativity, intelligence, and collaboration as important characteristics of scientists.

The findings indicate that children tend to associate scientists with visible stereotypes, such as being older individuals with unusual hair or working constantly in laboratories. At the same time, they appear less likely to recognise the positive and realistic aspects of scientific work, including creativity, intelligence, and teamwork. These results, therefore, reveal a stereotypical and largely negative perception of scientists among the children. The findings highlight the need for educational interventions that can promote a more accurate and balanced understanding of scientists and the nature of their work.

Children's Stereotypical Views of Scientists

Table 4 presents children's stereotypical images of scientists based on various indicators from the DAST.

Table 4. Indicators of Stereotypical Images of Scientists in Students' Drawings (N = 40)

S/N	Variable	Indicators of Stereotypic Image	f	%
1	Scman	Scientists are depicted as men	31	77.5
2	Scwoman	Scientists depicted as women	9	22.5
3	Whitecoat	Scientists dressed in white coats	27	67.5
4	Glasses	Scientists wearing glasses	11	27.5
5	Labtool	A drawing showing laboratory tools	28	70
6	Techtool	Drawing showing technology tools	4	10
7	Location	Scientists working in a laboratory, library, or office	25	62.5
8	Dishevelled	Scientists have crazy hair	15	37.5
9	Unfriendly	Scientist portrayed as serious or angry	26	65
10	Biochem	Biochemistry or chemistry field	26	65
11	Astrophys	Astronomy or astrophysics field	1	2.5
12	Math	Mathematics field	0	0
13	Environ	Environmental science, botany, or zoology	0	0
14	Technol	Robotics technology or informatics engineering	2	5
15	Artshum	Arts and humanities	0	0
16	Medicine	Medicine	0	0
17	Multidis	Depicting two or more research areas	8	20
18	Formula	Drawing showing formulas or numbers	0	0
19	Expt	Experimenting (actively testing or discovering)	22	55
20	Think	Thinking (e.g., looking up)	4	10
21	Teach	Teaching (e.g., writing on a classroom board)	2	5
22	Crazy	Scientist portrayed as violent or unpleasant	10	25
23	Danger	Elements indicating danger (e.g., explosions)	1	2.5
24	Unsafty	Scientists did not wear safety items	33	82.5
25	Solitary	Scientist represented alone	37	92.5

The results reveal strong and common stereotypes among the children. A majority of children (77.5%) perceive scientists as male, while only 22.5% associate scientists with women. Most children associate scientists with wearing white lab coats (67.5%), laboratory tools (70%), and glasses (27.5%). Additionally, 37.5% identified crazy or wild hair as a characteristic feature of scientists.

A large proportion of children (62%) believe scientists work in laboratories, libraries, or offices, and 92.5% perceive scientists as working alone rather than collaboratively. Many children (65%) depicted scientists as serious or angry, and 25% viewed scientists as violent or unpleasant. Notably, 82.5% of the depictions showed scientists not wearing safety items, indicating a misconception about laboratory safety practices. Children mostly associate scientists with chemistry or biochemistry (65%) and largely overlook other fields such as astronomy (2.5%), robotics (5%), mathematics, environmental science, arts, and humanities (all 0%). More than half (55%) associated scientists with experiments or active testing, but very few linked them to thinking (10%), teaching (5%), or the use of technology tools (10%).

These results highlight prevalent and narrow stereotypes of scientists as predominantly male, working alone in laboratories, often serious or unfriendly, and frequently neglecting safety practices. These limited views exclude many important aspects of scientific work and diversity in the field. The findings suggest a need for targeted educational programs to broaden children's understanding and appreciation of the diversity and collaborative nature of scientists and scientific work.

Children's Misconceptions about Science

Figure 5 presents the mean scores and standard deviations for children's misconceptions about science. The overall mean score of 3.03 (SD = 0.76) indicates that children demonstrate a moderate understanding of science. Higher mean scores were recorded for negatively worded statements such as "Science is only for people who are good at math" (M = 3.38, SD = 1.61) and "Science is not a creative field" (M = 3.30, SD = 1.44). These responses suggest that some children perceive science as a field that requires strong mathematical ability and one that lacks creativity. Such views reflect common stereotypes that portray science as inaccessible and overly technical.

Lower mean scores were observed for other negatively worded statements, including “Science is a static field that does not change much over time” (M = 2.80), “Science is not relevant to everyday life” (M = 2.83), and “Science is only about biology, chemistry, and physics” (M = 2.85). The relatively lower ratings for these items indicate that many children recognise that science evolves, extends beyond a few traditional disciplines, and plays an important role in everyday life. The findings suggest that although children hold some stereotypical views about the difficulty and creativity of science, they also demonstrate an awareness of the dynamic, interdisciplinary, and socially relevant nature of scientific knowledge.

Figure 5. Means and Standard Deviations of Children’s Misconceptions about Science

Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that children generally hold positive attitudes toward science, particularly in recognizing its relevance to everyday life and its role in addressing real-world challenges. Recent studies have similarly reported that young learners tend to value science when it is presented as meaningful and connected to their daily experiences (Rommel AlAli & Al-Barakat, 2024). This positive orientation reflects an emerging instrumental view of science, where learners perceive scientific knowledge as useful and applicable. However, the persistence of perceptions that science is difficult or boring among some children suggests a disconnect between recognizing the value of science and experiencing it as engaging. Research on inquiry-based and student-centred science instruction demonstrates that when learners actively construct knowledge through exploration and problem solving, their interest, motivation, and enjoyment of science significantly improve (García-Carmona et al., 2025).

The findings of the present study align with a substantial body of literature demonstrating that children’s early experiences with science play a critical role in shaping not only their STEM literacy but also their perceptions of science and the work of scientists. How science is represented to children, both within classrooms and through broader cultural and media influences, significantly affects how they understand who scientists are, what they do, and who belongs in science (Thomson et al., 2019). Across studies, children’s perceptions consistently reflect stereotypical images of scientists, suggesting that such views are formed early and may persist unless explicitly addressed through instruction.

These stereotypical images appear to intersect with children’s attitudes toward science and their developing science identities. While many children report enjoying science, research suggests a gradual decline in interest over time (Lei et al., 2019; Murphy & Beggs, 2003). Lei et al. (2019) found that children were more interested in doing science than in being scientists, and although they initially expressed confidence in their ability to perform science tasks, both interest and self-efficacy tended to decrease with age. Similarly, Murphy and Beggs (2003) observed that younger children held more positive attitudes toward science enjoyment than older children, despite older students reporting greater confidence. These

findings suggest a disconnect between engagement in science activities and identification with science as a long-term pursuit.

Children's enjoyment of science is consistently linked to hands-on, exploratory experiences. Across studies, students reported that conducting experiments, particularly those involving unexpected outcomes or visual effects, was the most enjoyable aspect of science learning (Murphy & Beggs, 2003; Dickson et al., 2021). However, Dickson et al. (2021) highlighted a tension between enjoyment and authenticity, as many children perceived classroom science as fundamentally different from the work of real scientists. Students frequently described classroom activities as overly structured, with predetermined outcomes and teachers who already knew the answers, leading them to view school science as lacking genuine discovery (Dickson et al., 2021). This perception may further contribute to declining interest and difficulty in forming strong science identities.

In this study, many children relied on stereotypical portrayals of scientists as older, socially isolated males working alone in laboratories. Such findings are consistent with recent research showing that dominant images of scientists continue to be characterized by gendered and social stereotypes (Losh et al., 2025). Identity-based perspectives suggest that these representations influence learners' self-concepts and shape their beliefs about who can participate in science. When children repeatedly encounter narrow and exclusionary images of scientists, they may struggle to see science as a domain in which they belong, particularly girls and students from underrepresented backgrounds (Carlone & Johnson, 2007; Archer et al., 2015).

Similar to the findings of the present study, Brumovska et al. (2022) reported that children's perceptions of scientists could be categorised into five distinct profiles: Brainy, Crazy, Supernatural, Clumsy, and Normal scientists. These profiles commonly portrayed scientists as highly intelligent individuals, often characterised by a dishevelled or eccentric appearance and frequently associated with experiments that result in explosions or fires.

The misconceptions identified in this study, such as viewing science as static, discipline-bound, or lacking creativity, highlight persistent gaps in students' understanding of the Nature of Science (NOS). Contemporary NOS frameworks emphasize that scientific knowledge is tentative, empirically grounded, theory-laden, creative, and socially embedded. However, recent empirical evidence suggests that many students continue to hold naïve views of science as a fixed collection of facts rather than an evolving process of inquiry (Tripp et al., 2024). Such limited understandings may constrain students' epistemic engagement and reduce their appreciation of science as a human and creative endeavour, thereby weakening both conceptual learning and affective engagement.

The stereotypical representations evident in children's drawings further reinforce concerns related to both NOS understanding and science identity development. The frequent depiction of scientists as solitary individuals in laboratory settings mirrors patterns documented in recent studies, which show that stereotypical images of scientists emerge early and remain remarkably stable over time (Avşar Erumit et al., 2025). These portrayals conflict with contemporary views of science as collaborative, interdisciplinary, and socially relevant. Such entrenched images may limit students' ability to form inclusive and realistic understandings of scientific practice and participation. Similar studies have shown that children commonly depict scientists as male, working indoors in laboratory environments, and surrounded by chemistry-related equipment such as test tubes, flasks, and glassware (Bernard & Dudek, 2017; Samaras et al., 2012; Thomson et al., 2019; Leavy et al., 2023). These representations point to a narrow conception of scientific work, heavily centred on laboratory-based natural sciences and procedural experimentation. The continued predominance of male scientists in children's drawings and descriptions, as reported by D'Addezio and Besker (2024), further highlights the persistence of gendered stereotypes in children's scientific imaginaries. Such portrayals may limit children's ability, particularly girls, to identify with science and envision themselves in scientific careers.

Beyond gender and setting, children frequently associate scientists with particular personality traits and behaviours. Studies have reported both positive and negative characterisations. Scientists have been

described as intelligent, hardworking, curious, and dedicated, but also as eccentric, socially detached, or even dangerous (Ruiz-Mallén et al., 2018; Samaras et al., 2012; Brumovska et al., 2022). Brumovska et al. (2022) identified distinct profiles such as Brainy, Crazy, Supernatural, and Clumsy scientists, illustrating how fictional and media-driven narratives shape children's understanding of scientific work. The association of science with explosions, danger, or extraordinary abilities reinforces misconceptions about the Nature of Science and obscures its collaborative, evidence-based, and human dimensions.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have important implications for science teaching and curriculum design at the basic education level. First, science instruction should explicitly address the Nature of Science, emphasizing its dynamic, creative, and socially embedded character. Inquiry-based, project-based, and problem-centered learning approaches allow students to experience science as an active process of knowledge construction rather than a static body of facts, which has been shown to positively influence students' attitudes and conceptual understanding (Ganajová et al., 2025).

Second, educators should deliberately challenge stereotypical images of scientists by incorporating diverse scientific role models across gender, ethnicity, age, and disciplines. Classroom resources such as biographies, multimedia materials, and interactions with scientists can help broaden students' perceptions of who scientists are and how scientific work is conducted. Exposure to collaborative and socially relevant scientific practices is particularly important for supporting inclusive science identity development (Shakil et al., 2025).

Finally, science teaching should intentionally support science identity formation by creating inclusive learning environments in which all students feel capable of meaningful participation. Encouraging student voice, valuing multiple ways of knowing, and recognizing creativity within scientific inquiry can help learners see themselves as legitimate participants in science. When students perceive science as accessible, relevant, and reflective of their own identities and experiences, they are more likely to develop sustained interest and aspire toward future engagement in science-related pathways (Carlone & Johnson, 2007; Archer et al., 2015).

Teaching science during the early childhood years is widely recognised as foundational for the development of scientific thinking, inquiry skills, and positive dispositions toward science learning. Trundle (2005) argues that young children are naturally curious and capable of engaging in meaningful scientific exploration when provided with developmentally appropriate, hands-on learning experiences. Rather than emphasizing formal scientific content, early childhood science instruction should focus on observation, questioning, prediction, and simple investigations embedded in everyday contexts. This perspective aligns with constructivist views of learning, which emphasise active engagement and knowledge construction through interaction with the environment. Research reinforces these principles, demonstrating that inquiry-based and play-oriented science activities enhance conceptual understanding, language development, and problem-solving skills among young learners (e.g., Fleer, 2021).

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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